

PARALINGUISTIC MEANS IN DIFFERENT LINGUACULTURES

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Annotation

The article examines and conducts a typological analysis of paralinguistic means in multi-system languages. When comparing gestures, facial expressions and body movements, the author is based on their form (kinesic), meaning and distribution; the nature, meaning, and functions of paralinguistic means in communication are studied; issues of incorrect interpretation of gesture semantics are touched upon, which can subsequently lead to significant errors in formal communication in international communication.

Keywords: paralinguistics, nonverbal communication, gesture, sign, verbal and nonverbal sign, social differentiation, kinesics, proxemics, phonation

Prominent linguist E.D. Polivanov wrote back in 1919: "...the meaning of words is supplemented by various modifications of the sound side, which mainly includes the melody of the voice tone (in addition to it, there is also the tempo of speech, various degrees of sound strength, different shades in the sound-producing works of individual organs, for example, sluggish or energetic activity, etc.), and, finally, gestures. One should not think that these aspects of the speech process are something that is not subject to linguistics, i.e., the science of language. Only, of course, the consideration of these facts (memorization, gestures and other accessories of speech) constitutes a special independent department of linguistics, by the way, this is the department by which linguistics comes into contact with the theory of dramatic art."

In modern linguistics, the special field of linguistics mentioned above by E.D. Polivanov, in a broad sense, is called "paralinguistics", and the means that this field in charge of are called "paralinguistic means".

Currently, paralinguistics significantly expands its aspect of research; it includes numerous means accompanying human speech communication, namely articulation-acoustic types of phonations or simply "phonation", as well as human gestures and facial expressions, commonly referred to by the term "kinesics". In writing, "graphic signs" (in handwriting) perform paralinguistic functions.

The study of the interaction of verbal and nonverbal means reveals certain patterns in the coordination of certain gestures and different parts of speech, gestures and syntactics of statements; the processes of a kind of mutual enrichment of verbal and

nonverbal units are interesting — all this is included in the linguistic aspect of the problem proper.

It is difficult to summarize and compare all the gestures, facial expressions and body movements used in English, Uzbek and Russian communication. Therefore, we compare only those gestures and facial expressions that are often used in communication. When comparing gestures, facial expressions and body movements, we base on their form (kinesic), meaning and distribution. A significant sign of a gesture is usually called a “kineme” (comes from the term “kinesics”), and its variants are “kines”, “allocons”, the latter are rare.

Gestures and facial expressions follow from the situation of the content of speech, its emotional intensity, are inseparable from the movement of thoughts and feelings. Rhythmically coordinated with intonation, accents and pauses, gestures and facial expressions help to focus the interlocutor’s attention on certain most important parts of communication, to express the speaker’s emotional attitude to the thoughts expressed.

In paralinguistic terms, it is necessary to clearly distinguish human movements that participate in nonverbal communication. These are, first of all, gestures that are created by conscious or unconscious movements - mainly the head, face (including eyes), body parts, depending on or independent of verbal speech, simultaneously or alternatively serving as a means of communication: manners, more or less dynamic and behavioral, as well as socially ritualized, according to specific communication situations; poses are equally conscious and unconscious, but more static, as well as codified by social norms and used less as a communicative behavior, and poses can be associated with gender, status, culture, etc. Another difference in kinesics refers to movements of a free and limited type. Free movements are themselves performed by one or several parts of the body, whereas limited movements occur when other parts of the body, things and objects interact. Movement, like articulation of sounds, has three phases: the beginning (the pose of silence), the central moment and the end of the movement. These three phases of kinesic behavior are created by the parakinesic qualities of intensity, distance, and speed. As F. points out. Poyatos, the totality of all phases of a gesture has “semantic value”.

Not all movements have the status of a gesture. It is necessary that the movement, first, have a symbolic character. A person can stretch his hand forward, bend over, sit, stand up, and it will not be a gesture. Movement will be a gesture only if not only practical, but also symbolic meaning is attributed to it. For example, “a person greets (or says goodbye).” In addition, the gesture should have a communicative orientation: the gesture is always addressed to another person, or at least assumes the presence of some kind of external environment.

Despite the long tradition of studying gestures and facial expressions of peoples, many issues remain controversial, however, "... a naive idea of the universality of certain significant gestures, as well as movements of the head and facial muscles, easily arises."

Any ceremony, diplomatic reception, official meeting, banquet turns a person's behavior into a certain sequence of gestures, and any participant in such ritualized situations has to reckon with the fact that any of his movements can be "read" as a gesture and interpreted in one way or another.

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Nonverbal parakinesic means by their functions can be classified as follows:

- 1) gestures that replace language (for example, a greeting or farewell gesture);
- 2) gestures accompanying the language, accentuating gestures (for example, the gesture of highlighting important things in speech);
- 3) Symbolic conditional gestures (for example, the gesture of "saluting" in the military);
- 4) emotionally expressive gestures (for example, a gesture of threat, reproach, reprimand, etc.);

Gestures are also widely used in the methodology of teaching foreign languages. In this regard, M. West writes: "Language is a form of behavior, it is the reaction of the organism as a whole to the surrounding social environment, and words are only part of this reaction, which, among other things, also includes posture, facial expressions, and gesture."

Knowledge of proper verbal and non-verbal means of communication contributes to the deep study of foreign languages.

It is impossible to transfer the symbolism of gestures adopted in the culture of

one people into the culture of another people, because of which there can be no full-fledged communication or it becomes difficult, that is, parakinesic interference appears.

If we proceed from R. Jacobson's very fair remark, then national "dictionaries" of gestures can differ significantly both in volume and in specific content. Their relationship with other means of communication, and above all with language, also varies. If we do not take into account such specific gestures as in deaf-mutes, in whom they approach the status of language, then complementarity relations are most often observed between speech utterances and gestures. Gestures can accompany speech, illustrate it, and act as a separate "replica" in the overall structure of communication.

There are other principles of gesture classification. Initially, having distinguished the actual gestures (kinesics) and sound gestures (phonation), it is possible to distinguish gestures of high tonality (oratorical gestures), neutral-everyday (used in public places), familiar (e.g., patting), vulgar, etc. Naturally, the general norms of gesticulation adopted by different peoples also differ (in a simplified form: from restrained among northerners to temperamental among southerners).

Various social, professional and confessional groups have their own standards and some differences in the "dictionary of gestures", not to mention the differences in the composition and use of gestures among men and women, adults and children. The issues of gesture semantics become especially important in international communication. Errors in interpretation occur mainly with a formal coincidence: a similar gesture is given the meaning that it has in its culture. For example, a diametrically opposite distribution of head movements in affirmation and negation is observed in Uzbeks, Russians, Bulgarians, Englishmen and Americans. There are oppositions between various gestures of kinesic content, just as linguistic units (phonemes, morphemes, word meanings) are in opposition. For example: consent-denial ("yes" and "no" in gestures and facial expressions), greeting-farewell, movements of the right and left hands (right-left hand), gestures of joy - gestures of anger, etc.

In general, the picture of the human world is built with the help of a certain set of oppositions - such as life - death, happiness-unhappiness, male-female, etc. Among them, spatial oppositions (top-bottom, inner-outer, right-left) are of fundamental importance, which underlie the entire multidimensional (not only spatial) system of human orientation in the surrounding world. One of the features of spatial oppositions is that they can acquire an evaluative meaning. This is especially characteristic of the opposition "right-left". "Right" is associated with *"truth", "right", "rightness", while "left" is associated with a lie ("crooked"), "wrong", "wrong".* A positive value is most often attributed to the right, and a negative value is attributed to the left.

Different peoples use parakinesic means as symbolic elements in different ways. The gesture is an iconic nonverbal element and forms a number of oppositions. Moreover, it can be associated with the semiotics of a linguistic sign and can be converted into units of language at the lexico-grammatical level.

Certain contents are transmitted not only with the help of verbal speech, but also with the help of non-verbal means - gestures, facial expressions and body movements. The meanings of parakinesic means can be determined by a certain environment, respectively, representatives of different peoples differ from each other in mimic behavior, the nature of gestures, although analogies can be found in the functional relationship between verbal speech and non-verbal means, nevertheless it is impossible to talk about the exact correspondence of an extra-linguistic gesture and a word as linguistic units.

The geographical distribution of some gestural and mimic signs often covers a large territory and, accordingly, we can talk about the universality of certain gestures and facial expressions, but their meaning may not coincide among different peoples. Consider the gestures and facial expressions of affirmation and denial. The comparison of the two opposite means of affirmation and negation is based on the movements of the head. As R. Jakobson pointed out, the Russian binary system of signs of affirmation and negation coincides with the mimic sign of the vast majority of European countries. Similar signs in the same function are generally widespread among other peoples of all parts of the world.

The jerk of the head here serves as an expression of consent, in other words, a synonym for the word "yes", which is also observed among the Turkic-speaking peoples, in particular, among the Uzbeks.

The nod of the head finds a close analogy in the ritual of greeting many peoples, including Uzbeks, Russians and Englishmen. The movement of the head forward and down serves as a visual representation of the worship of the requirement, desire, suggestion or opinion of the interlocutor, it also embodies an obedient readiness for an affirmative answer to a positive statement of the question. The direct opposite of the head, bent forward as if in a sign of obedience, should have been the head, thrown back as a sign of disagreement, disagreement, refusal, simply a negative position. There is even a persistent emphatic repetition of both an affirmative and a negative mimic sign. For example: "*Ноп бо'ladi!*", "*Да, да, да*", "*Yes, yes, yes!*", "*Yo'q, Yo'q bo'lmaydi!*", "*Нем, нем!*", "*No, no, no!*" with a forward-backward movement of the head when asserting and can similarly convey negation.

The movement of the head from top to bottom corresponds to the speech "yes", i.e., it can act as an independent sign without a speech text. A nod of the head is a

universal, polysemantic gesture. Its form coincides with the form of greeting, but its distribution does not coincide, since, depending on specific contextual situations, it is understood as consent or greeting.

In the Russian language there is a group of verbs related to the paralexics, which express gestures and facial expressions “yes” and “no”, i.e., consent and denial. Such verbs are used as if as para-lexical synonyms in the text and replace extra-linguistic gestures and facial expressions.

For example, “nod” – “nod, nod your head to someone”, “agree”- “agree with a nod of the head”, i.e., once or repeatedly tilt and raise your head again. At the same time, the eyes may look at the interlocutor or be lowered. [1;121] Agreement with the interlocutor's opinion, willingness to respond to a request or invitation may be accompanied by the words: “yes”, “good”, “I'm ready”, “of course”, etc.

In the Uzbek language, there is also a group of verbs expressing consent: “*bo'shini o'ldingga chayqamo'q чайкамок*”, “*boshini qimirlatmo'q*”, “*kallasini qimirlatmo'q*” (“*кивать*”- “*кивнуть головой*”). This movement is also accompanied by the expressions “*ha, hop, boladi*”, “*mayli*”, “*mayli-da*”, “*ha mayli*”, “*albatta*”, “*shunday*”, “*huddi shunday*”, “*shunaqa*”, “*haqiqat*”, “*to'g'ri*”, “*juda to'g'ri*”, “*ro'st*”, “*ro 'st aytdingiz*”, etc.

In English, an affirmative gesture is represented by nodding the head from top to bottom, which is accompanied by the expressions “*yes, all right, right, o-yes, very well, of course, certainly, yes, please, sure, surely*”, etc.

In English, the gesture of approval is conveyed by the verb “to nod” –one's head) - to nod/nod your head, “to nod assent”, “to nod one's approval” - “to nod approvingly”.

In English, an affirmative gesture is represented by nodding the head from top to bottom, which is accompanied by expressions “*yes, all right, right, o-yes, very well, of course, certainly, yes, please, sure, surely*.”

In English, the affirmation gesture is conveyed by a verb “to nod” (one's head) – кивать/кивнуть головой, “to nod assent”, “to nod one's approval”- “кивать одобрительно”.

As for the gesture of denial, repeated rapid turning of the head to the right and left is typical for Uzbeks, Russians and Englishmen. In the Uzbek language, there are complex verbs for expressing negation “*boshini (kallasini) chayqamoq*,” “*boshini (kallasini) ikki tomonga qimirlatmoq, boshini likillatmoq*, т.е. “множественно быстро поворачивать голову вправо и влево”.

This negative gesture is accompanied by statements like “*yo'q-yo'q, bo'lmaydi*”, “*noto'g'ri*” “*to'g'ri emas*”, “*yolg'on*”, “*bo'lmagan gap*”, “*ishonmayman*”, “*hech-da*”, “*yug'-e*” u m.d.

Nonverbal means of communication give credibility, which can be determined by

facial expressions or body movements, while for verbal it is impossible to say with certainty about the veracity of the interlocutor. A person can nod with an expression of affirmation, but not at least at the same time nod quite affirmatively.

Europeans, especially the British and Americans, usually keep their arms crossed on their chests, which means denial. A tense emotional state forces a person to accept this gesture, and the preservation of the gesture supports internal tension. An affirmative nod of the head is a positive gesture used to express “yes” or approval, as well as a negative shake of the head with the meaning “no” are considered innate gestures. Moreover, a negative shaking of the head, according to a number of scientists, is the first innate gesture of a person.

Another gesture expressing a negative attitude of a person is a gesture when the head is tilted down, or sitting with the head down and arms folded on the chest. This gesture is also universal and is found among the British, Russians and Uzbeks. According to A.Nurmonov, the horizontal movement of the head of the Uzbeks expresses the negation of “йўқ”- “no”, and the vertical movement of the head means the statement – “boron” – “yes”. Moving your head forward and down means approving the interlocutor and approving his statements. The head thrown back means refusal, denial or disapproval of the interlocutor's opinion in Uzbek communication. Interestingly, the form of Uzbek communication coincides with the form of Bulgarian negation, in which “... the head thrown back - away from the interlocutor, embodies withdrawal, disagreement, warm-up, rejected offer, refusal of a positive answer to the question asked ...”

We compared gestures that are involuntarily observed and have some invariants in each communication, due to the social and national-cultural characteristics of peoples. Consideration of various symbolic gestures, the so-called “metaphoric”, is not part of our task.

The typology, built on one basis - functional, allows for a comparative analysis of nonverbal communication in various areas and social structures, as well as to determine the communicative role of nonverbal means in related use. A communicative unit in the connected functioning of verbal and nonverbal signs is a verbal utterance, in which nonverbal signs act as communicative components that concretize semantic, evaluative and social information.

The paralinguistic level has a powerful communicative potential and occupies an important place in natural communication. Verbal and nonverbal communication systems function in close interaction and complement each other, and sometimes replace each other, due to the commonality of basic

functions and the difference in structural and system characteristics of verbal and nonverbal signs.

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